

Assessing Leadership Competencies through Social Network Analysis

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Abstract. Leadership competencies are regularly identified as some of the most in demand workplace competencies. However, the development of these competencies requires appropriate assessment that are often either highly subjective (e.g. manager appraisals) or prohibitively expensive (e.g. roleplays with trained actors). Moreover, these assessments are often performed periodically and with little consideration for when leadership behaviours are actually exhibited. The increasing usage of workplace social networks and increasing prevalence of digital collaboration tools presents a continuous stream of social interactions that can contain evidence of leadership occurring in situ. In this paper we present initial research on the feasibility of Social Network Analysis in the workplace to assess leadership competencies. We examine the feasibility of such an assessment in terms of content, construct, and criterion validity. We then present our hypotheses on how the assessment can be conducted including the algorithms necessary to extract relevant features from a social network graph model. Our initial research, to our surprise, shows a weak correlation between individual's degree centrality and betweenness centrality and the leadership competency that is self-reported. However, experiments indicated a strong positive correlation between network structure based and social collaboration activities based features and the characteristics of the leadership competencies. We conducted statistical comparison of our self-reported leaders with others within a ranked set of users based on social network features. We then trained a set of machine learning models to categorise users in the social network into users who show leadership characteristics (leaders) and users who don't (non-leaders). Our initial experiments achieved an AUC score of 0.899 when social network features were leveraged along with social collaboration activity based features to distinguish individuals with self-reported leadership competencies from others. Finally we discuss our findings on the practicality of the approach, and future work on validating and improving the results obtained using parallel conventional assessments for leadership competencies.

Keywords: assessment, leadership, social network analysis, great eight, competencies

1 Introduction

The assessment of transversal competencies and skills, are predominantly realised through subjective self-rating questionnaires and interviews [23, 27, 32]. Although certain skills such as problem solving are readily assessed in narrow domains such as mathematics, generalizable assessments remain elusive [32]. Although behavioural interviews and situational judgement tests are also used [23], they are relatively uncommon as their cost and susceptibility to rehearsal, respectively, limit their appeal. The design of soft-skill assessments, in general, is challenging for a number of reasons. The multidimensional nature of these skills, their expression most readily occurring during execution, and the typical absence of a resulting artefact, are obstacles to summative or self-reported assessments [17]. Moreover, these skills typically vary between situations and contexts, where some fuzziness in the definition of the skills is also likely [12].

To realise an effective assessment, clarity is needed on what is being assessed and what instruments are being used. Specifically, there is a need to clarify competency models and social network analysis, respectively.

1.1 Competency Models

As work and jobs vary extensively there are numerous competencies and competency models available (e.g O*NET [28], ESCO [11]), there will be little distinction and nuance between them, or as Bartram [3] states "Clearly a balance is needed between highly differentiated models that may not be generalizable and overly broad constructs that fail to capture relevant general dimensions of performance"[3]. To ensure re-usability it is necessary to implement a competency framework that is universal enough to apply to most jobs within a variety of organisations. In order to do so a trade-off is needed between specificity and generalisability.

Kurz and Bartram [22] conducted extensive work on developing a generic competency framework. Bartram [3] distinguished a framework of 112 very specific competencies at the finest level of detail, so called competency components. These competency components are clusters of workplace behaviour. Bartram [3] states that "... these components can be thought of as building blocks that can be aggregated together to produce competencies. Sets of competencies, in turn, form competency models..." [3]. The research aggregates the 112 components into eight general factors. Based on their work, Kurz, Bartram & Baron [21] propose a general competency model which distinguished eight general factors, also called the Great Eight.

The Great Eight structure provides an articulation of the work performance domain that is consistent with a wide range of models used by practitioners in competency practice and supported empirically by the way in which competency ratings cluster when subjected to factor analysis (e.g [20, 21]). The Great Eight factors [3] are:

- Leading and Deciding
- Supporting and Cooperating
- Interacting and Presenting
- Analysing and Interpreting
- Creating and Conceptualising
- Organising and Executing
- Adapting and Coping
- Enterprising and Performing

This work uses the Great Eight factors as the base competency model that is reusable across diverse jobs and organisations.

1.2 Social Network Analysis

Social Network Analysis (SNA) - a recent development in sociology, is a technique of analysing individual's social links arising from social interactions, their formation, evolution and impact. Recently SNA has gained popularity by its ability to solve complex problems in various domains of an individual's life due to the availability of large digital footprints of the social data. Social network data is modelled as a graph where individuals are *nodes* and any "connection of interest" between nodes are *links*. With this graph model of relational data, analysis is possible at various levels; at the node level for the analysis of node's position in the network, at the network level for global structural analysis, and at the dyad level for analysis of links and their properties [5]. Generally, in SNA, special consideration is paid to nodes and network characteristics. The following are basic metrics that can be used for node characteristics:

Degree Centrality is the number of links a node has with others. This indicates the connectedness of a node. In case of directed graphs degree centrality has two forms *in-degree centrality* and *out-degree centrality* which could be the indicators of a node being prominent or influential respectively. The basic idea is that many others seeking to connect to a node (in-degree) is a sign of importance of that node and a high out-degree could indicate the node's ability to reach many others and disperse information more quickly which could be thought as exerting influence.

Closeness Centrality shows a node's reachability to others in the network. It is the measure of a node's *geodesic path* distance to all other nodes in the network. It is normalized (range=(0,1)) and gives indication of node's reachability to others. In the context of this paper, closeness centrality is a measure of node's influence on others and is calculated using Hubble approach [4] in which all pathways are considered between two actors and weight of each path is assigned using an attenuation factor of 0.5.

$$CC(u) = \frac{n-1}{\sum_{v=1}^{n-1} d(u,v)} \quad (1)$$

Betweenness Centrality shows the node's role as connector in the shortest paths between any two nodes in the network. It determines the relative importance of the node in terms of other's dependency on the node. It is defined as:

$$BC(v) = \sum_{s,t \in V} \frac{\sigma(s,t|v)}{\sigma(s,t)} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma(s,t|v)$ is the number of shortest paths from node s to t via node v and $\sigma(s,t)$ is the total number of shortest paths from s to t .

Eigenvector Centrality is also a measure of node's influence. It is an extension to degree centrality but unlike degree centrality it considers inequality in connections of the node's neighbours.

Structural Holes as Social Capital: A node is considered to span structural hole in a social network if it is linked to parts of the network that are otherwise not well connected otherwise [8]. It is argued that nodes with large number of structural hole spanners have advantage of getting access to unique information through friends who do not know each other [7]. In the workplace, applications that foster collaboration among employees such as blogging applications can be considered as spanning structural holes, in that, they facilitate interactions between employees who would otherwise not be able to find each other. The concept of being in an advantageous position from the information access point of view if a node bridges a structural hole in the network is exploited in this paper. We associate structural hole benefits of having access to unique information with the structural effectiveness of node's ego network and quantify it with three measures as proposed by [7]

1. *Constraint (CT)* - It is the extent to which a node is constrained by its connections. The lower the better - Low constraint value of a node indicates less dependency on its connections. It is defined by [8] as:

$$CT_{ij} = p_{ij} - \sum_q p_{iq} m_{jq}, q \neq i, j \quad (3)$$

where m_{jq} is i 's interactions with q divided by j 's strongest relationship with anyone and p_{iq} is the proportion of i 's energy invested in relationship with q which is constant as $\frac{1}{N}$, where N is number of nodes in the network.

2. *Effective Size* - Measure of non-redundancy in the connections of a node. The higher the better - Less number of redundant connections increases employees chance of accessing more unique information. It is defined by [8] as:

$$ES_i = \sum_j \left[1 - \sum_j p_{iq} m_{jq} \right], q \neq i, j \quad (4)$$

3. *Ego Network Efficiency* - It is the measure of quantifying the effectiveness of connections on the node. The higher the better - More efficient network reduces redundant information.

2 SNA as an assessment method

The use of SNA to assess transversal competencies is promising as it is formative, continuous, based on on-task evidence, and flexible across situations and contexts. However, this approach faces inherent challenges:

- Sampling: Captured social network evidence is a proxy for actual social interaction, it is unlikely to capture the full scope of social interactions.
- Ambiguous Intent: It may not be clear as to why a social interaction happened, its purpose, and its positive or negative nature may be unreported or ambiguous.
- Availability: Evidence may not be available due to circumstance (small teams, availability of digital social tools), organisational policies (e.g. security), and legal restrictions (e.g. data protection). The challenge of incomplete data has been noted by [16].
- Universality: Where a social network is built by the necessity of a job role, its usefulness as a predictor of individual traits may be limited. In the case of personality assessment, it has been found that SNA can be a poor predictor for managers as their social network is required and not elective [8].
- Coverage: Valid assessments incorporate observations of the skills being assessed. The focus of SNA on network interactions and structure inherently limit it to those skills evidenced through social interactions.

There is a need for reliability, validity, objectivity, and feasibility in assessments [17]. Further requirements include the need for assessments to be "clear and consistent; technically sound, using valid and reliable observations, data and inferences" [12].

The use of social network analysis to assess transversal competencies addresses several of these requirements, as well as the challenges faced by existing approaches. Its objectivity is highly desirable, especially in light of the prevalence of unreliable manager observations [27]. Its reliability over time is likely to be good, although calibration and verification of the algorithms will be needed. However, feasibility is a considerable challenge for this approach. The ability to obtain sufficient social network data for any individual in light of the data actually existing, it being representative of the individual, and legal and ethical requirements have been considered, is a significant obstacle. Moreover, the benefit incurred from the assessment results would need to exceed the cost of gathering and processing this data.

The remaining challenge is that of validity. Although intuitively the approach possesses high validity due to focussing on actual on task behaviour, the assessment needs validity in terms of content, construct, and criterion [17].

Content Validity. In terms of content validity, the nature of the social interactions would need to align with the competency or skill under assessment. In the case of assessing collaboration, the SNA evidence would need to represent collaborative activities such as co-authoring or meetings, as opposed to non-collaborative activities such as broadcast marketing or periodic email updates.

In particular, the Great Eight competency factors of Leading & Deciding and Supporting & Cooperating will be the focus of this work.

Construct Validity. In terms of construct validity, there is supporting research to justify identifying individual traits through SNA, particularly in terms of personality [2, 8, 13, 15, 19, 31, 33]. However, the direct assessment of workplace transversal competencies through SNA is so far, an under explored area.

In several instances SNA has been used to identify attributes of groups (explicit and latent) that impact overall task performance. These attributes can be derived from various network metrics. It was found that direct ties positively influence innovation output of teams, although increasing structural holes in interfirm networks can have the opposite impact [1]. The calculation of clusters and cliques can be used to identify cohesion, a central component of collaborative learning [30], whereas the use of network density and out-degree centralization was also found to indicate cohesion [24]. In the area of shared leadership, low network centrality based on leadership behaviours can indicate better sharing of leadership responsibility as opposed to the high centrality of a single leader [26].

For the characteristics of individuals, the research is less prevalent. However, the use of closeness is related to positive performance on learning tasks, a result in contrast to other non-learning task

research [9]. This work also showed that communication styles were associated with different ego network compositions. Additionally, the use of network centrality was found to correlate with leadership reputation for known leaders. However, the effect was context dependent and was evident in networks of subordinates, but not in networks of high-ranking supervisors [25].

Overall the use of SNA to assess specific competencies is evidently limited with little consensus on the metrics in use or the competencies assessable [16]. However, there is growing interest in focussing on attributes of individuals to provide insight in the broader organisational performance.

"Theory that links individual attributes to structural outcomes is likely to be generative of compelling research. Such research might fruitfully include the characteristics of all members of the network in order to explore the possibility of complementary synergies between actors and network structure." [18]

Despite the limited research in this area, there is evidence to support the likelihood that with due consideration of context, SNA for competency assessment has construct validity.

Criterion Validity. To evaluate the criterion validity of the approach we will investigate the concurrent and predictive validity of how SNA assessment agrees or predicts the results of other assessments such as 360 degree reviews [6], game-based assessments [29] and self-reported personality tests [14]. Within the DEVELOP research project [10], these parallel assessments are available for the competencies focussed on.

2.1 SNA features of interest

The novel nature of using SNA for individual competency assessment leaves limited insight into the network characteristics resulting from specific competencies. For this reason, this research is largely explorative in nature. However, the following specific hypotheses were investigated.

Direct assessment of competencies through SNA. The use of network observations captured digitally, as they happen, creates a chronological dataset, an attribute missing from previous work that used network surveys or untimed friend networks. This availability of timed interactions may correlate with competencies related to Deciding & Initiating Action. In particular, it may correlate with the Great Eight competencies of *Acting on Own Initiative*, *Acting with Confidence*, and *Taking Action*.

H1 The initiator of first social interactions, and bursts of social interaction is a predictor of Deciding & Initiating Action competencies.

The competency of Providing Direction & Coordinating Action requires a high level of communication and social interaction.

H2 The network centrality and relative frequency of interactions is a predictor of Leading & Supervising competencies.

The expression of competencies in the work place relating to leading, deciding, supporting, and cooperating, creates observable social interactions that affect the social network structure. These structural changes may be distinct enough to predict these competencies.

H3 Network structure and Social Capital characteristics predict Leading & Deciding and Supporting & Cooperating competencies.

3 Social Network Feature analysis/extraction

3.1 Data Sources Description

We conducted our experiments in a large multinational organization using following datasets. An irreversible MD5-hashing technique was used to anonymize and align the records across all the datasets.

1. *Enterprise social network (ESN)* - This is a “friendship” social graph of employees in the enterprise and it has more than $100k^4$ nodes and millions of edges between them. The edges are directed where one terminal node of a particular edge indicates the node who initiated the “friend request”.
2. *Collaboration activity streams* - Second dataset contains a large number of activities performed by employees on an *Enterprise collaboration platform - IBM Connections*, for a period of over 2.5 years (Jan 2014- June 2016). Collaboration activities include “creating/commenting/linking” a blog, “joining/following” a community, “tagging/following” others, “creating/commenting/linking” someone’s status update.
3. *Self-reported leaders* - In addition to social network and the collaboration data, we also had a number of employees (approx. 2200) who completed a “Leadership Development Programme” between June 2016 and Aug 2016 within the organization and their profiles were tagged with a “leadership” tag, which was self-reported as well as endorsed by others in the organization. In this paper, we consider this set of employees as having leadership competency and this is our ground truth.

3.2 Experiment Settings

In this paper, we approach validation of our proposed hypotheses in two steps: First we extract three different sets of features for each user in our datasets where each set characterise the social behaviour expected from a user having leadership competency as discussed in previous section. To identify the employees who show the leadership characteristics, we use social structural features to statistically compared them with users who don’t show leadership characteristics.

In the second step we further demonstrate the construct validity of SNA technique for leadership competency assessment by leverage the extracted features in a machine learning binary classification task. The objective of supervised learning in our case is to see if employee’s social behaviour can be used to characterize an employee from the leadership competency point of view. To evaluate our machine learning models, a k -fold cross validation approach was adopted, which randomly divides the dataset into k subsets and trains model with $k - 1$ subsets while testing it with one left over set. This process is repeated k time, with each of subset used exactly once as the testing set. In this paper, we used 10-fold cross validation. To quantify the model evaluation, we adopted two measures in this paper, AUC and precision due to the the fact that our dataset was extremely imbalanced in terms of ratio of positive labels with negative (approx. 1 : 100). AUC can be interpreted as probability of randomly chosen employee with leadership competency has higher score than randomly chosen employee with no leadership competency. AUC can be calculated as defined in:

$$AUC = \frac{n' + 0.5n''}{n} \quad (5)$$

where n' is number of times employee with leadership competencies have high score, and n'' number of times missing links and non-existent links have same score out of n comparisons.

Precision is the ratio of correctly predicted individuals with leadership competency. All the missing links are first ranked in decreasing order according to their predicted score. If l is the number of positive instances correctly predicted out of a sample (let’s say L), then precision is:

$$precision = l/L \quad (6)$$

⁴ We are not able to reveal actual numbers here and throughout the paper for commercial reasons

4 Results & Discussion

4.1 Results of Explorative analysis

H1: The initiator of first social interactions, and bursts of social interaction is a predictor of Deciding & Initiating Action competencies.

To get deeper insight into the characteristics of employees with leadership competencies, in a first step, we looked at how connected these users are. To do so, we compared their network degrees with average degree of the social network. The average degree ($\langle k \rangle = 331$) of 2573 leaders was 8.5 times higher than average degree for the rest of the network ($\langle k \rangle = 39$). However, when leaders were compared to the average degree of their neighbours, only 31% users with leadership tag had higher degree than their immediately connected nodes. Based on this observation, we derived two rankings: first, we ranked users with respect to their number of out-degree (high value of out-degree is indicative of user as “source” of friendship request in our directed social network) and number of created blogs respectively. We compared the top 1% segment of both user rankings. We observed average of social activities which involve *taking an own initiative* (e.g. creating a blog post, sending a friend request) was higher for leaders than the non-leaders. We observed a combined 60% of top 1% ranked users in out-degree and blogs-creation leaders and their averages were much higher than non-leaders (average out degree of 602 for leaders compared to 438 for non-leaders and average blogs created by was 70 compared to 41 for non-leaders) (as shown in Figure 1). This is also confirmed by our comparison analysis of leaders vs non-leaders in Table 1. We can see top 1% ranked users in features that characterise user as taking action on own initiative contain the highest overlap of leaders.

Fig. 1: Comparison of initiating actions like SNA features for leaders vs Non leaders

Table 1: Overlap between leaders/non-leaders and the users with high number of action in collaboration streams and high Out-Degree

leaders vs non-leaders	out Degree			#blogs created			#comments on blogs			# blogs liked			total visits on created blog		
	Top 1%	Top 5%	rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest
leaders (%)	17.17	8.71	0.07	11.28	6.21	0.36	6.99	3.63	0.75	1.96	1.56	0.65	12.43	6.33	0.37
non-leaders (%)	82.83	91.29	99.93	88.72	93.79	99.64	93.01	96.37	99.25	98.04	98.44	99.35	87.57	93.67	99.63

H2: The network centrality and relative frequency of interactions is a predictor of Leading & Supervising competencies

For H2, we mined collaboration activity streams to identify and analyse users actions which can be considered as evidence of their competency to supervise others. To this end, we extracted two features for all the users in our dataset; (i) ‘number of employee user has mentored’, (ii) ‘a yes/no flag based on user’s history if he/she has mentored others or not’. In addition, to supervising evidence, we analyzed employee’s centrality in the ESN. We applied in-degree centrality, closeness centrality, betweenness centrality, local clustering co-efficient and eigenvector centrality to employee’s social network and ranked them for each centrality measure to be classified with respect to the categories top 1%, top 5%, and ‘rest’. Table 2 shows the percentage overlap for leaders and non-leaders in their respective categories. Results of this analysis reveal that 7.51% of top 1% ranked employees who mentored others are leaders and this percentage gets smaller for other two categories. Our analysis shows that leaders not only depict the behaviour of supervising other but are also central in their respective social networks. In particular, the results for closeness centrality reveal that leaders are generally close to all others in the network: 19.24% of the top 1% leaders users belong to the category of the top 1% users with respect to closeness centrality. However, unlike the global measures of centralities, results indicate that leaders have very low overlap in Local Clustering Co-efficient (LCC) and overlap slightly increase with low ranked users (top 5% and ‘rest’ category). This might be understandable if when the context of LCC is considered. LCC is the degree to which nodes tend to bind together in triangles locally. It can also be thought as a measure ‘openness’ or ‘closeness’ of a node’s social network. Lower value of LCC means more open a node’s network and more opportunities for the node to connect with others in the network. This network characteristic might be desired for a leader’s social network as network openness allows leader’s to connects with diverse individuals who themselves are not connected and ultimately access to unique information.

Altogether, our analyses of the ESN for this H2 hypothesis shows that many users with leadership characteristics are among the best-connected users in the ESN. This holds for all centrality measures taken into account.

Table 2: Overlap between leaders/non-leaders with users of high centrality and higher evidence of supervising others

leaders vs non-leaders	# employees mentored			Closeness Centrality (CC)			Betweenness Centrality (BC)			Eigenvector Centrality (EC)			Clustering Coefficient (CLCO)		
	Top 1%	Top 5%	rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest
leaders (%)	7.51	2.26	0.84	19.24	8.06	0.05	3.37	2.47	0.33	7.95	7.5	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.07
non-leaders (%)	92.49	97.74	99.16	80.76	91.94	99.95	99.63	97.53	99.67	92.05	92.5	99.95	99.96	99.94	99.93

H3: Network structure and Social Capital characteristics predict Leading & Deciding and Supporting & Cooperating competencies

Social capital measures are indicative of a user’s ability to utilise resources in the network. In this paper, we leverage measures proposed by Burt [7] to quantify the social capital in the form of user’s local constraint (CT), effective network size (ES) and efficiency (non-redundant connections) in user’s ego network. Generally, an individual with high social capital is expected to have high ES and efficiency but lower constraint value in his/her ego network [5, 7]. Our analysis reveal that there is high positive correlation between social capital measures and individuals with leadership characteristics. Our experiments demonstrate that in top1% ranked users in constraint category have no leaders and overlap increases for 5% and ‘rest’ category, whereas percentage of leaders in top5% is high for effective size and efficiency measures. If we consider the definition of constraint which is *the extent to which a node is constrained by it’s connections to reach others in the network*. It is expected that for leaders in the organization, less of constraint measure is desired and leader’s social network is expected to be more open and less redundant as per our discussion for H2. This is the kind of the behaviour proposed by our H3 hypothesis and is shown by individuals with leadership characteristics in our results. Since

Fig. 2: Comparison of supervising and network centrality features associated with H2 for leaders vs Non-leaders

in our proposed H2 and H3, there is overlap in characterising leading&supporting characteristics of the leaders from their network structure perspective, these results in a way confirms both hypotheses.

Summing up our analysis on network structure and social capital to characterize leadership competency, our analysis reveal that top 1% ranked users in the social network have high overlap in depicting a supportive behaviour towards others (i.e. they have high number of others with whom they have shared their expertise). Additionally, they have high structural social capital as shown by high overlap for measures such as effective size and efficiency along with low overlap in local constraint.

Table 3: Overlap between leaders/non-leaders with users of social capital measures and high evidence of supporting others

leaders vs non-leaders	#employees shared expertise with			Ego Network Constraint (CT)			Efficiency (EFF)			Effective Size (ES)		
	Top 1%	Top 5%	rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest	Top 1%	Top 5%	Rest
leaders (%)	10.17	4.35	0.69	0.00	0.07	6.25	10.51	6.00	0.07	18.02	8.86	0.05
non-leaders (%)	89.83	95.65	99.31	100	99.93	93.75	89.49	94.0	99.93	81.98	91.14	99.95

4.2 Results from classification analysis

To further demonstrate the ability of our extracted features as potential characteristics of user’s leadership competency, we trained a set of supervised machine learning models to categorize users with “leadership” tags in our ground truth dataset. A Box and whisker plot comparison of trained algorithms is shown in Figure 4. Input to our classification models are a set of features based on employee’s social activity, network structure and social capital extracted from the ESN and activity streams. The extracted features are believed to be the indicators of behaviours described in our hypotheses and the associated Great Eight competency cluster.

We can observed that out all the trained models, eXtrem Gradient Boosting (xgb) performed the best. Therefore, we further trained xgb to get the best score in terms of AUC. The best score achieved with xgb is AUC of 0.899.

Fig. 3: Comparison of supporting others and one of social capital features associated with H3 for leaders vs Non leaders

Fig. 4: Box and Whisker Plots of various ML models trained for leaders vs Non leaders classification

5 Conclusions and future work

The use of SNA for competency assessment is both promising and under developed. In the absence of research attributing causal relationships in this area, DEVELOP will be explorative in identifying such relations. We have demonstrated the usefulness of SNA for competency assessment through a set of features extracted from a real-world enterprise social and collaboration data. Our experiments have shown that users with leadership traits depict a set of behaviours that can be captured from their network structure and social capital characteristics to assess their leadership competency. However, there are certain limitations associated with direct assessment of leadership competency through SNA in terms of its validity and we were only able to show construct validity of SNA for competency assessment. Other validity measures of SNA as highlighted at the start of this paper are not

demonstrated here and we envisage to further investigate them in our future work. As part of future work outlined hypotheses will be tested as part of the DEVELOP evaluations by gathering leadership competency assessment data through other direct or indirect methods such as personality assessment, 360 degree feedback, GMA assessment and serious-game simulation. This research will contribute to the state-of-the-art in social network analysis for transversal competency assessment.

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